

RUNNING HEAD: MEDICAL CLAIMS, DEATH WARRANTS, AND POLLING DATA

Medical claims, death warrants, and polling data: the Fletcher model

Abstract

In 2004, Ernie Fletcher, governor of Kentucky and licensed physician, brought on an ethical controversy of first impression by signing a death warrant for Thomas Clyde Bowling. A coalition of doctors, death penalty opponents, and medical students waged a very public campaign criticizing Fletcher for violating the Hippocratic Oath, and submitted a formal complaint to the Kentucky Board of Medical Licensure demanding that he lose his license to practice medicine. The study examines this controversy for insights into the ways argument creates, challenges and manages identity, particularly under conditions of extreme role stress.

On November 8, 2004, much as on any other day, Ernie Fletcher took care of the paperwork that went with the job. It seems unlikely that he knew, as he worked, that he had just given the first push to an ethical snowball. Handling the paperwork itself was a somber occasion, but a reasonably good career move; one year, to the week, after Fletcher had been elected governor of Kentucky, he signed his first death warrant for a condemned prisoner, Thomas Clyde Bowling (Yetter, 2004a). The previous governor, Paul Patton, had ordered the first two executions since the Supreme Court's reinstatement of capital punishment, and had turned back a bill to abolish it in Kentucky (Chellgren, 2000) with little public reaction, so Fletcher likely was unprepared for the argument set in motion by this exercise of his authority. However, there was one important difference between himself and Patton, and that difference would entangle Fletcher in a crisis of role stress.

In argument, the element of arguers' *identity* has drawn spotty attention. From Ehninger's (1970) observation that people who join in argument put their identities at mutual risk, to a more extended discussion of the factor inspired by Hazen & Williams (1997), many scholars have attended to it in prefatory comments and asides, and a few have addressed it as the core of a sustained work. Antczak (1990) explains that the choices made by arguers lock them into a persona, reasoning from a pattern of claims William Seward developed in response to the pre-Civil War slavery crisis to the conclusion that "public figures constitute their characters in argument; they talk themselves into being, into a practical public identity – into some of the specific possibilities and limitations for word and action with which they must subsequently contend" (p. 1108). While argument scholarship conventionally analyzes the rational merit of arguments and argument practices, this argument-borne identity draws from the *relational* content of the messages; the more compelling identity arguments are "those which stimulate the individual's (or collective's) desire and willingness to associate" (Hazen & Williams, 1997, p. v).

This practical public identity is at constant risk of being overcoded, as through the ongoing struggle of a controversy “arguments define identities that may not be consistent with each arguer’s self-image” (Kline, 1986, p. 243). The choice of argument projects an identity to other participants, but their replies also shape the image.

While for very prominent and visible figures, this may primarily or entirely involve their unique individual identity, far more often argument shapes *collective* identities, tweaking the norms attached to public roles (Hazen & Williams, 1997; McKerrow & Bruner, 1997). Ernie Fletcher’s critical difference from Paul Patton was not his biography, his image, or his personal skill set; it was a formalized, discursively constituted role that abides near the top of the hierarchy of social roles in most cultures. Ernie Fletcher was only the fourth U.S. governor ever to hold an M.D. And on November 8, 2004, he became the first licensed physician since the adoption of the AMA’s binding code of ethics to order a man put to death as punishment for a crime.¹ Thomas Clyde Bowling had been convicted of killing a young husband and wife one morning as they arrived to open their business. As he sat on death row, his attorneys deployed a creative array of appeals: Bowling was mentally retarded, there was no formal protocol for lethal injection in Kentucky’s laws, new evidence suggested another person may have been involved in the killing. And Ernie Fletcher was a licensed physician, so his decision to sign the death warrant arguably violated both the Hippocratic Oath, and the laws of Kentucky which criminalized breaches of the AMA’s code of medical ethics (Yetter, 2004c).

This was hardly the first time someone had questioned the ethics of a physician taking part in an execution. Medicine and the death penalty have a venerable association, from Dr.

¹ “According to the National Governors Association, there have been three other doctors who have been U.S. governors since the AMA guidelines took effect in 1980. But none was in the position of having to decide whether to sign a death warrant. Dr. Otis Ray Bowen of Indiana left office in 1981 without signing a death warrant. Vermont, where Dr. Howard Dean spent 12 years as governor, has no death penalty. Dr. John Kitzhaber was governor during two executions in Oregon before leaving office in 2003. But the Oregon governor does not sign an execution warrant - a judge does. Kitzhaber could have granted clemency to the condemned but chose not to” (Barrouquere, 2004, ¶ 13-14).

Joseph Guillotin's 18th century campaign to win acceptance of the machine later named for him (Baum, 2002), to Drs. Carlos MacDonald and E.C. Spitzka's 19th century pursuit of the same objective, thankfully without gaining a macabre namesake, for the electric chair (Ragon, 1995), to Dr. Stanley Deutsch, whose detailed recipe for a lethal injection allowed Oklahoma to codify the method in law in 1977, and Texas to carry out the first such execution in 1982 (Tuohy, 2005). Nevertheless, many physicians resist any involvement with an execution because, they say, it turns the healing art on its head: doctors' most bitter enemy is death, doctors' ultimate failure is death, and so doctors who deliberately causes death commit treason against their role no less stark than judges who accept bribes, or parents who choose to harm their children. The American Medical Association splits the finest of hairs in forbidding, in its model ethical code, all but the most passive medical contact with any execution: doctors may not *pronounce* the condemned person dead, but after someone else has done so, they may *certify* the death, acting *only* to confirm the performative conclusion of the penalty (American Medical Association [AMA], 2005). At the same time, many states require the presence of a doctor at executions, and some states' protocols call for the doctor to taken an active part, creating a double-bind in which "The physician cannot make an ethical choice" (Salguero, 1986, p. 168). Baum (2002) warns that as questions about the fairness of capital punishment grow in urgency, "central to that evaluation is the appropriate role for the scientific community, and particularly the medical profession, in the accurate and ethical implementation of that punishment" (p. 50).

And yet, all Ernie Fletcher did was take pen in hand and sign his name to a piece of paper. No class in medical school, no experience during his residency, equipped him with skills that would be needed to *order* the execution carried out. Thus, the complaint, joined by medical students and anti-capital punishment activists, raised a case of first impression to be debated by the public, by professionals, and by formal governing bodies: did Ernie Fletcher's involvement in

Bowling's punishment violate medical ethics, even though Fletcher used absolutely no medical knowledge or technique in carrying out his part?

With a physician serving as Senate majority leader, six physicians in the House (Lawrence, 2004), and another physician having moved from front-runner for the Democratic presidential nomination to chair of the Democratic National Committee (Kornblut, 2005), it seems as though Governor Fletcher's death warrant might not be the last instance of a doctor ordering, under her or his own authority, that a person be put to death as punishment for a crime. Senator Frist, when he speaks to audiences of doctors, urges them to enter politics (Vandewater, 2003). The role stress that arises when a licensed doctor is called upon to serve as decisionmaker in a capital case demands resolution, and the arguments generated as the medical community attacks the issue should generate a bountiful harvest of clues to the contours of the collective identity of doctors.

In the sections that follow, I will analyze the controversy surrounding Fletcher's death warrant for characteristics of identity creation, challenge and management through argument. I will begin by examining the ways doctors' roles are constituted and their norms generated and maintained, then survey the controversy over doctors' participation in carrying out capital sentences. Then I will examine the arguments presented by Fletcher's critics and defenders, including Fletcher's own words. Finally, I will summarize my findings.

Review of literature

Three scholars have contributed useful pieces to this puzzle about the professional identity of doctors: Ken Gatter, Arthur Applbaum, and Donald Judges. Gatter (1999) charts the relationships between medical authority and legal authority, identifying the elements that encyst deliberation on medical controversies within the community. He catalogs exhaustively the techniques that medical school professors use to socialize medical students into novice initiates

into the medical guild: intensive coursework and testing, isolation from outsiders, disciplinary moves during oral exams and rounds, and maintenance through board exams and specialization. Once the newcomers are cemented into their web of relationships with other medical professionals, no outside influence can budge their decisions: judges, legislators, all rely on the word of trained medical professionals to explain disease, medical practice, proper behavior of doctors, and virtually all other matters that are open to question. Gatter further pinpoints the gap between science, which, to outside observers, appears to be the foundation of medical knowledge, and *appropriateness*, a concept employed by doctors to explain the variation in practice from one office to another. Because each illness is unique, each injury unique, each patient unique, and each doctor's judgment unique, the combination cannot be observed, tested, and the results replicated in a scientifically satisfying fashion; instead, doctors judge other doctors only on the appropriateness of the practice, or its location within the acceptable range of choices a well-trained doctor can make. Thus, doctors are dependent on a consensus formed within their community to maintain their authority and autonomy against such interference from the outside world as malpractice charges.

Appelbaum (1999) builds upon Gatter's model, explaining that there is only limited potential for outside criticism of medical practice. He argues for *role positivism*, or an understanding of role as being little more than what its practitioners are doing at any moment. Speaking in particular of the medical profession, Appelbaum warns that if too many restrictions are placed upon doctors, they'll simply announce that they have adopted a different identity – Appelbaum whimsically names them “schmoctors” – and continue practicing according to their own lights. Despite this fortification against outside challenges, Appelbaum offers hope that medical practice can be held to a high standard of propriety, not through regulation and punishment, but through *argument*:

The profession of doctoring must therefore understand itself as a calling that could have been otherwise, but argue why it still is a calling worthy of being answered by a reflective practitioner. Insofar as doctors continue to identify with their profession, and look to their colleagues for guidance and support on what counts as good professional practice – that is, insofar as those with medical training wish to subject themselves to the judgment and approval of their peers – they will reject the label of schmooctor. The challenge, of course, is to continue to articulate in a clear and reasoned voice to both doctors and patients what would be lost if the practice of doctoring gave way, in substantial measure, to the various forms of schmooctoring that I have described (p. 60).

Applbaum warns that efforts to blunt or thwart medical autonomy are futile, and even undesirable if they were possible, but harnessing the pride and stubbornness that accompany such authority is a more effective and desirable approach to steering medical practice toward the ideal.

Of the three, only Judges (2004) directly addresses doctors' entanglement with executions. He develops two ideas which shed light on this controversy. First, Judges warns that even if wardens and judges join with bioethicists to win the argument over the ethical permissibility of doctors' involvement, the "considerable *psychological cost*" to the doctors (p. 518, emphasis mine) is an undiscussed factor. He examines arguments in the lethal injection controversy and discovers moral disengagement, borrowing the framework from Bandura et al. (1996), in arguments that diffuse responsibility among multiple decisionmakers, downplay proximity of preparatory acts to the lethal act, and otherwise rationalize participation through convoluted reasoning. Judges also contrasts *thin* medical ethics, or ethics that answer the question "Have I behaved unethically," from *thick* medical ethics, or ethics that answer the question "What identity have I created for myself?" He urges doctors to treat their ethics as *thick* in departures as egregious as participation in an execution.

The argument

The complaint filed against Fletcher was neither accidental nor a spur of the moment decision; rather, it was a single high profile move in the broader strategy of a handful of anti-death penalty activists. Arthur Zitrin, like Ernie Fletcher, is a physician, but Zitrin is also a member of the American Bar Association's Committee on Capital Punishment (Richardson, 2004). He admits that his efforts to end doctors' participation in executions has "been a quixotic effort in some respects" (Robeznieks, 2004, ¶ 7), but one to which he has devoted ample time and energy policing threats to the collective identity: "I think it's a totally improper role for a physician to be complicit with the state in killing people, because it's not the role of a doctor to do that. The role of a doctor is to heal and to preserve life whenever there is a possibility of doing so" (Campos, 2005, p. 1A). Jonathan I. Groner, who directs the trauma unit of Columbus Children's Hospital in Ohio (Crane, 2004), worked to organize the complaints against Fletcher on medical ethics grounds, calling his alliance "rag-tag," but enough to make doctors "uncomfortable" by drawing attention to their role transgression. Other participants in the argument include the Kentucky Coalition to Abolish the Death Penalty (KCADP), headed by the Reverend Patrick Delahanty, (Biesk, 2004), and a group of thirty medical students at the University of Kentucky medical school, Fletcher's alma mater (Musgrave, 2004).

The complaint came in two parts: first, Fletcher was violating his Hippocratic Oath by signing the warrant; second, Fletcher was violating the law, which incorporated the AMA's code of professional ethics into Kentucky state law. The medical students began their letter, even before mentioning the death warrant, asking Fletcher to "remember and respect the value intrinsic to the health profession, that first and foremost we must not harm" (Text of, 2004, ¶ 1). Dr. Stewart Urbach, one of the signers of KCADP's letter, reasoned, "The basic Hippocratic

Oath is 'do no harm,' and execution does irreparable harm” (Kentucky Governor’s, 2004, ¶ 5).

KCADP’s press release included an even more specific criticism:

Dr. Ernie Fletcher, Governor of Kentucky, abandoned his professional oath when he signed a death warrant ordering the killing of Thomas C. Bowling by the State of Kentucky. An active physician and licensed by the state of Kentucky to practice medicine, Dr. Fletcher is bound by the oath every doctor takes. In part, it states, “I will give no deadly medicine to anyone if asked nor suggest any such counsel.” (Kentucky Coalition to Abolish the Death Penalty, 2004, ¶¶ 2-3)

Finally, one of Fletcher’s political rivals, Democratic state representative Jim Wayne, perhaps sensing a good sound bite, contrasted his loyalties: “It’s curious he will keep his no-new-taxes pledge but will violate his Hippocratic oath. I’m not sure how he sleeps at night with this kind of decision” (Barrouquere, 2004, ¶ 16.)

For some, the charge that Fletcher had violated the oath would ring hollow. Various commentators have dismissed the Oath as obsolete (Baum, 2002; Davis, 1995), too doctor-centered at the expense of patients’ autonomy (Hasday, 2002), and so full of anachronisms that most medical schools edit it to the point of unrecognizability before administering it to their students (Colburn, 1991). Others view the Oath in the same light as founding documents such as the Magna Carta or the Declaration of Independence: while its precise phrasing may not serve to capture the current state of medical ethics, it does provide the medical community with a heritage, strengthening its cohesion and streamlining its norm-maintenance (Markel, 2004; Lucas & Pross, 1995). Smith’s (1996) historic research documents a pattern of increased use of the Hippocratic Oath as a graduation ceremony at times when the medical community is under siege from outside criticism. And, in particular, the Oath does more than set apart a collection of *practices* that must be performed carefully and deliberately; more than that, it establishes an

identity for those who would claim authority to carry out those practices: “Its essential purpose was to identify the Greek group of physicians as healers who would never kill or harm their patients” (Curran & Casscells, 1980, p. 227).

Violating the Hippocratic oath might sully Fletcher’s reputation as a doctor, and might put him squarely at odds with images of beneficence and healing, but would not function as on-point criticism of his job governing the state, so the second element of the charge pointed out that he was violating Kentucky’s laws. The medical students’ letter continued, “We also remind you of Kentucky state law, which states ‘No physician shall be involved in the conduct of an execution’” (Text of, 2004, ¶ 3). Of course, what was left open to question was whether signing a death warrant, far removed in space and time from the execution chamber, constituted “participation.”

The core of Fletcher’s defense was the claim that he operated in multiple roles, and that those roles could be deactivated while he carried out actions antithetical to their demands. He told Fox News, “There is a distinct difference between acting as a physician for a patient and acting as a governor for the people of the commonwealth of Kentucky” (Kentucky Governor’s, 2004, ¶ 2). Hogan told reporters, “The governor signed the warrant while carrying out his responsibilities as governor. In no way does this conflict with the ethics of the governor's private profession” (Yetter, 2004, ¶ 12).

The complainants had a good deal to say in response. In their letter to the Kentucky Board of Medical Licensure, KCADP asked,

The basic question is whether or not a physician who voluntarily takes on an additional role in life, that of an elected Governor, is thereby shed of the responsibilities and ethical duties he has assumed in his role as physician. Do medical ethics apply only to the doctor-patient relationship? Can Dr. Fletcher while maintaining his medical license

simply say, “Thomas Bowling is not my patient,” and ethically sign his death warrant?
(Costanzo et al., 2004, p. 3)

Groner answered the question, posing a vivid hypothetical:

Not only has Governor Fletcher never renounced this oath, but he also demonstrates his status as an active physician by holding a current Kentucky medical license. If Governor Fletcher was at an official state function and a guest keeled over from a heart attack or a ‘cafe coronary,’ would he fail to render aid on the grounds that he is the governor and therefore not required to act as a physician? Of course not. Why? Because the ethical tradition of the medical profession - which demands that physicians be healers and not killers - is over 2,400 years old. (Groner, 2004, ¶¶ 2-3)

Zitrin drew the issue back to its parameters: the question was not whether Fletcher was a bad person in the abstract, but whether he could continue to be licensed as a *physician*, given such conduct: “But I believe that a physician is not freed of his obligation to comply with his profession's ethical mandates. If Fletcher wanted to forgo that obligation, he should have surrendered his license when he was elected” (Zitrin, 2004, p. B11). Finally, the KCADP letter called into question whether Fletcher’s prior behavior had kept his roles distinct: “The question may be compounded by the fact that in his campaign for Governor and while serving as Governor, Dr. Fletcher has naturally enough expressed pride in being a physician, and has on occasions rendered medical treatment to those in need” (Costanzo et al., 2004, p. 3)

In fact, Fletcher seems to call upon one role to bolster his efforts to perform the other quite freely. Campaigning for Congress, Fletcher concluded his stump speech on medical malpractice reform with the plea, “I am uniquely qualified. As a physician, I play a major role in good, and affordable health care” (Bratcher, 2000, ¶ 18). On another occasion, he told an audience, “As a family physician, health care is an issue I've spent my adult life addressing. I

promise to stand by a patient's bill of rights” (Nelson, 2000, ¶ 9). Upon being elected governor of Kentucky, he outlined a list of cost-containment proposals in his inaugural address, concluding, “As a physician, I am especially dedicated to improvements in this area.” (Fletcher, 2003, ¶ 46) And in his 2005 State of the Commonwealth address, Fletcher called “upon my fellow physicians” (2005, ¶ 135) to address the problem of over-prescribing. At times his language was even more vivid and concrete; addressing malpractice reform on the gubernatorial trail, Fletcher warned, “For the sake of Kentucky's patients we must stop this hemorrhaging. My prescription for the problem is to call for a constitutional amendment that will grant the governor and legislature the authority to tackle the medical malpractice issue” (Biesk, 2003, ¶ 6). Even the Hippocratic requirement of nonmaleficence which he later would be accused of violating was called into play as a sound bite; while still in Congress he warned against radical moves in health care reform: “The lesson I took out of that is like the Hippocratic Oath: First, do no harm. I respect what the other doctors are trying to do. But I'm afraid their plans would just make things worse.” Later, after coming under fire during a gubernatorial candidate debate for voting against legalizing the importation of prescription drugs from Canada, Fletcher told an interviewer, “I knew when I voted against it that it would be an attack issue. But as a physician, I took a Hippocratic oath to do no harm, and some of these drugs are dangerous” (Harris, 2003, p. C2).

Was a physician's identity continuous, or could s/he deactivate it under certain circumstances to participate in actions that gravely transgressed the Hippocratic ethic? Previous writings on the permissibility of physician participation in lethal injection had grappled with this issue, but the results had been mixed. Many drew the line at application of medical knowledge or technique: if a doctor used *doctor skills* to commit an anti-Hippocratic act, then that constituted an ethical infraction (Dworkin, 2002). Others argued that the proper motive for anyone to enter medical school was a commitment to the *value* of care, meaning that the taint of participating in

an execution struck to the heart of a physician's *integrity* (Michalos, 1986; Sikora & Fleischman, 1999). A stinging review of physician participation, compiled by the American College of Physicians, Human Rights Watch, the National Coalition to Abolish the Death Penalty, and Physicians for Human Rights (1994), warned that entanglement with capital punishment gave the impression that doctors as a whole approved of the death penalty, which damaged public trust in their commitment to healing. Unfortunately, the deliberations had never reached a situation in which the doctor did not apply medical skill or knowledge, but instead gave the command that the execution was to be carried out without further delay. The measures of involvement for Fletcher's participation in Bowling's death sentence stretched in opposite directions: it was more distant than typical medical tasks, including examining the condemned and certifying death, but at the same time it was far more necessary, because the sentence could not be carried out until the governor ordered prison officials to proceed.

A corollary of Fletcher's core defense, developed in occasional comments to the press, was to spread responsibility for the execution to other parties, a move predicted by Judges as a dissociation move designed to minimize the psychological impact of carrying out an execution. To a Fox News reporter, Fletcher said "I felt the jurors made a sound decision, and I wanted to recognize they made a sound decision and acknowledge that by signing the death warrant" (Kentucky governor's, 2004, ¶ 7). This argument grew into a claim of obligation, a duty to carry out the will of the citizens expressed in their verdict. In a statement released to reporters, Fletcher employed the obligation argument to attempt to shut down further discussion:

As Governor with responsibility vested in me by the people of the Commonwealth of Kentucky and after thorough review of the case of Mr. Thomas Clyde Bowling, Jr. by me and my general counsel, I have decided to honor the decision of the jurors and sign the warrant ordering the warden of the Kentucky State Penitentiary to carry out the execution

of Thomas Clyde Bowling, Jr., on November 30, 2004. Consistent with previous practices and consistent with the advice of legal counsel, I hope the press will honor my decision not to take any further questions regarding this decision. (Keller, 2004, ¶¶ 4-5).

The governor's general counsel, John Roach, made the case in even stronger terms, suggesting that Fletcher's membership in the medical community should make no difference in his decisionmaking if the conventional practice of the criminal justice system dictated otherwise:

By signing a death warrant, in no way is Governor Ernie Fletcher participating in the conduct of an execution. Governor Fletcher's role under the law is consistent with the roles of judges fulfilling their legal duty and jurors fulfilling their legal obligations regardless of their professions. While the Governor respects the view of those who oppose capital punishment, he must reject the absurdity of the position that, because the people of Kentucky elected a physician to serve as their Governor, they have effectively chosen to abolish the death penalty during his term of office. (Keller, 2004, ¶¶ 6-7).

KCADP took great exception to this constrained view of the governor's authority in their complaint to the medical licensure board:

The law gives the Governor/Doctor authority to sign the death warrant, but neither the law nor the Governor's oath of office require him to do so. He also has the authority not to sign a death warrant. He has the authority to commute the death sentence to life without possibility of parole, or to life without possibility of parole for a term of years. The Constitution and the law recognize the Governor both as an official and as a human being with moral judgment, and give him the flexibility and the right not to execute. In this instance the human being is Dr. Ernie Fletcher. Is it a violation of medical ethics for him to sign a death warrant for Thomas Bowling? (Costanzo et al., 2004, p. 4)

And while the analogy is best used sparingly, and has suffered from grave abuse in the past (Caplan, 1992), it is worthwhile to note that in a past founding, or re-founding, event in medical ethics, a group of doctors attempted to defend themselves against charges of grave breaches of medical ethics, in some cases putting concentration camp inmates to death under the pretext that they were sentenced to die, by insisting that a legitimately elected government had commanded them, and had codified the command into law, to participate in what would become archetypal transgressions of medical ethics. The doctors argued that they were powerless to refuse because the government's command had put their lives in danger if they did not comply. The judges, the Nuremberg tribunal, rejected this defense, insisted that they should have complied with the ethical requirements of medicine, and declared them criminally culpable for the deaths. One of the lead defendants was Karl Brandt, Hitler's personal physician, who had no face-to-face contact with the prisoners whose torture and death made up the charges; instead, he had sat in an office at a far remove and simply ordered the experiments carried out (Nuernberg Military Tribunals, 1949).

Discussion

Kline, Antczak, and Hazen & Williams demonstrated that collective identity is shaped through argument; arguers create an identity from the aggregate of their arguments, and those choices are challenged, shaped and overcoded by the rebuttals of other participants. The controversy surrounding Ernie Fletcher's decision to sign Thomas Clyde Bowling's death warrant is fundamentally a controversy about identity, about the persistence of a professional role. Fletcher argued that his roles could exist in tandem, that he could detach one professional role to carry out the tasks of another. Notably, while insisting that he would not give up his medical license, Fletcher allowed his role as governor to override his role as physician, rather than choosing the opposite set of priorities. One might assume the pursuit of medicine was a role

more entangled with a person's core values than the pursuit of political power, and thus more difficult to put aside when the two came into conflict. For Fletcher, this was not the case.

If Gatter's model accurately captures the dynamics of medical decisionmaking within a shell of autonomy, then the divide between Drs. Groner and Zitrin on one side and Dr. Fletcher on the other is a grave threat. Appropriateness is determined by consensus, and the very public charge of unethical conduct, including a formal attempt to strip Fletcher of his license, reveals cracks in that consensus. A recent AMA survey found that the majority of doctors are in favor of physician participation in executions (Klug, 2002). And, perhaps even more surprising, many physicians seem completely unaware that such participation even raises ethical questions (Liptak, 2004). The appropriateness of such participation, as a marker of the current state of medical ethics, is quite unsettled and in need of further development through deliberation.

If Applbaum is correct about role positivism, and the ease with which doctors can evade outside scrutiny simply by redefining their roles and renouncing old practice as obsolete, then Zitrin and Groner's strategy carries an enormous risk of backfiring. They admit that they have little hope of winning an across-the-board prohibition against physician participation in executions, arguing instead that the pressure they bring to bear consists chiefly of publicity and the accompanying embarrassment. And they have succeeded in changing the economics of capital punishment; formerly, the state of Georgia paid physicians \$850 to preside over an execution. Now, a consultancy firm has been formed to offer physicians professional liability insurance against exactly the kind of challenge Zitrin and Groner bring, and producing a doctor to solemnize an execution costs Georgia taxpayers \$18,000 (Campos, 2005, p. 1A). These efforts, by raising the profile of the issue and making physicians aware that such acts are at a minimum ethically troubling, may serve as the advocacy of role traditionalism that Applbaum recommends, but they may also serve as the pressure that pushes doctors to throw off criticism

and frame their own reconceptualized identity. It is notable that the language used by both sides was hardly conducive to reasoned deliberation: various commentators called Zitrin and Groner's complaint "an example of just how dirty politics can be" (Focus on, 2004, ¶ 4) and "nothing more than a cheap shot," (Criticism of, 2004, ¶ 3), while Zitrin paralleled Fletcher's ethical lapse with those of the commanding officers at Abu Ghraib (2004), and both he and Groner invoked Nazi atrocities (Groner, 2004). Fletcher's counsel, John Roach, called the complaint "an irresponsible game of political football," and his deputy general counsel, Michael Adams, labeled it "a backdoor attempt to abolish capital punishment during the governor's term of office," and concluded, "Though high on headline-seeking sensationalism, this grievance has absolutely no merit" (Biesk, 2005, ¶¶ 14-15), while Ray Larson, prosecutor in the Bowling case, dismissed the complaint as a strategy of desperation: "I think everything they're doing is a ploy. The fact of the matter is that every time there's a pending execution ... there's this mad scramble after all the legal appeals are heard to come up with whatever kind of excuses possible." (Yetter, 2004b, ¶ 12). It is possible that the fireworks are just preliminaries, no more than signals that each side is quite serious about its position, and that the more reasoned arguments described above will persist and will inform both sides in future cases. But it is possible as well that the heated language bodes ill for progress via deliberation toward mutual correction, as Ehninger somewhat idealistically suggested should be the outcome of argument.

Judges' framework captures two very important characteristics of this controversy. Fletcher has at no time defended his decision as squarely consistent with the ethics of medicine. He has not made the somewhat convoluted argument that capital punishment is a form of therapy and a way to respect the autonomy and individuality of the condemned, as others have attempted to do (Mossman, 1992). His defense has been entirely defensive: the actions were taken under a distinct role, so they did not constitute medical practice. Further, they were not his decision,

undertaken with his initiative, but rather simple ratification of a decision made elsewhere. Both are dissociation moves predicted in Judges' work, and both suggest psychological stress emanating from making, or at least defending, his decision. Furthermore, the gap between Fletcher's position and the position of the complainants demonstrates precisely the difference Judges describes between thin and thick ethics: Fletcher argues only that he has not committed an infraction and cannot be held accountable, while his opponents make a more nuanced argument that he has assumed a different identity and should no longer bear the title of physician.

Conclusion

On November 8, 2004, Dr. Fletcher became the first physician to sign a death warrant in possible violation of the American Medical Association's code of ethics. On January 13, 2005, the Kentucky Board of Medical Licensure voted unanimously to dismiss Groner and Zitrin's charge that Fletcher had violated medical ethics and should forfeit his license. The controversy opened up a fissure in the medical community's smooth consensus regarding appropriate practice. The arguments presented by each side followed patterns of deliberation on medical matters, but left unanswered the question of whether the ongoing deliberation would be productive, or the last exchange of communiqués before a rupture of dialogue and a defiant reassertion of control by doctors over their own identity.

On January 21, 2005, Peter Pilz, a member of the Austrian parliament, introduced a bill to strip Arnold Schwarzenegger of his Austrian citizenship. Earlier, Pilz's Green Party colleagues had circulated a petition to change the name of Arnold Schwarzenegger stadium in the city of Graz, near Schwarzenegger's birthplace. Schwarzenegger's fall from grace was a radical turn of events; just six months earlier, the Austrian government had released an Arnold Schwarzenegger stamp, and Austrian papers had been filled with commentary that Schwarzenegger would make a good president of the United States. The precipitating event that turned many Austrians against

Schwarzenegger was his refusal of last minute clemency to Donald Beardslee, a convicted serial killer. Within hours, Austrians were protesting outside the American embassy in Vienna. Pilsz's explanation for the revocation of Schwarzenegger's citizenship was, "Capital punishment is unacceptable in Austria and in Europe, and no Austrian citizen may take part in it or arrange it" (Kole, 2005, ¶ 17). And the toll of capital punishment-inspired role stress continued to mount.

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